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Discourse on Ecocriticism: A Review

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Abstract:

Ecocriticism is a branch of literature that studies the correlation between ecology and literature. And this paper aims to discuss the discourse on the synchronic and diachronic development of ecocriticism across the world. However, it starts in the West (especially America) and spreads throughout the world, either the East, the South or the North. Furthermore, the paper tries to raise awareness of the endangered situation of the environment and also discusses some of the critics who have worked in the field of ecocriticism.

Keywords: Ecocriticism, Literature, Synchronic and Diachronic, Endangered, Nature.

Ecocriticism as a literary theory primarily evolved in the 21st century by some American scholars. It is the blending of two words: ecology and criticism. Ecology is the study of the biotic and abiotic, which means the living beings like animals, trees, humans, etcetera, and the non-living things like air, water, sun, etcetera. Earth is the only known planet in this universe where

humans and other animals can survive. We are well aware of the importance of Nature in our lives. We are so dependent on nature that the resources we consume of it fall heavily upon the health and well-being of Earth. However, as we know, things exist in binary opposition. We are taking or consuming all the natural resources without giving back to nature. Moreover, this is creating the denaturalization of the ecosystem. As Devendra Kumar Sharma in his book review “An Indian Response to Ecofeminism: A Literary Study” (2024) explicates that “Today, we are living in a global era where capitalism has become the god of all religions and commercialization and consumption are the mantras of success”. (148). The gap between nature and human beings is getting wider day by day because of the growth and advancement of technology, science, and industrial development. Now everybody would like to live a comfortable and enjoyable life, and to achieve this, we are harming nature or the environment day by day. It is just an alarming time for us as we suffer the loss of different species and the problems of pollution, global warming, ozone depletion, deforestation etcetera. Although much awareness is observed world over which has called for the collective approach of the people to fight the challenges. One day was carved out to show such concern when on 22 April 1970 we began celebrating ‘Earth Day’. However, such type of celebration seems to be only customary and to bring an effective solution to the problem, we need to have some proper action plan and also its an effective implementation not only locally but globally.

William Rueckert is credited with coining the phrase ‘Ecocriticism’ in “Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism” (1978). Rueckert enunciates ecological fundamentals of poetry and language. However, the roots of this can be found in the past. As Scott Slovic in “Seasick among the Waves of Ecocriticism” (2016) enunciates:

After more than three decades of doing this work, I still cannot pinpoint the Urtext of ecocriticism, the absolute source, but I have the sense that ancient commentaries on the Dead Sea scrolls or the Upanishads, if they happen to refer to natural motifs in these works, would count as precursors to twenty-first-century discussions of the stories embodied in the lives of toads and stones and in the traces of industrial waste found in human bodies. (99)

Ecocriticism is the study of Ecology or Environment and literature. As William Howarth in his “Ecocriticism in Context” (2000) finds the etymology of ecocriticism from the *Oikos* which means household and *Kritis* which means to judge. *Oikos* represents nature/ household and *kritis* is “the arbiter of taste who wants the house kept in good order, no boots or dishes strewn about to ruin the original décor” (163). Ecocriticism has drawn the collaborative insights on philosophers, historians, critics, writers and “a vertiginous array of cross-disciplinary conversations with life scientists, climatologists, public policy specialists, geographers, cultural anthropologists, landscape artists, environmental lawyers, even applied mathematicians and environmental engineers ” (Buell, *Environmental Criticism* 5-6).

There are a number of associations, also those who have taken very important landmark steps regarding ecocriticism, like ASLE, ISLE, EASLCE etcetera. These associations help to spread ecocriticism from America to all over the world like the United Kingdom, South Korea, New Zealand, Bangladesh, Australia, India, Canada, Brazil, Japan, and among Southeast Asian countries.

In the starting two groundbreaking works, the Lawrence Buell’s *The Environmental Imagination* (1995) delineates the new ways to understand nature and humanities and emphatically, the

environmental crises have to show their prime concern in the texts. As he defines, ecocriticism is “the study of the relation between literature and environment conducted in a spirit of commitment to environmentalist praxis” (430). Further, Cheryll Glotfelty and Harold Fromm in *The Ecocriticism Reader* (1996) define ecocriticism is “the study of the relation between literature and the physical environment” (xviii).

Louise Westling in *The Green Breast of the New World* (1996) enunciates the interrelationship between environment and gender, class and race etcetera. Lawrence Coupe in *The Green Studies Reader* (2000) explicates critics and scholars from various schools like Formalism, New Historicism, Psychoanalysis, and Marxism etc., rejected the notion of nature because they believe that there “is no such thing as nature” (2). They included it within the cultural discourse, “a sign within the signifying system” (2). Kate Soper was against this notion and believed that it is not only a linguistic construct. As Soper in *What is Nature?* (1995) delineates that “It is not language which has a hole in its ozone layer; and the real thing continues to be polluted and degraded even as we refine our deconstructive insights at the level of the signifier” (151). She talks about the multiple meanings of ‘nature’. Further, she explicates that we have already destroyed our nature, and now it is our duty to conserve and preserve nature. Soper explicates different dimensions of nature in ecological discourse:

1. Nature as a metaphysical reality
2. In the socio-pragmatic discourse, nature connotes the meaning of structures, processes and the reality of the physical world.
3. In everyday use it refers to rural backgrounds, wilderness, animals, raw materials and the physical body. (*Ecocriticism: Theories and Practices* 2023, xv)

Similarly, Raymond William in *Keywords: A Vocabulary of Culture and Society* (1983) explicates, “Nature is perhaps the most complex word in the language” (219). Baruch Spinoza in *Ethics* (1677) delineates different dimensions of nature- *nature*, *naturans* and *nature naturata*. *Nature*, *naturans* includes paranormal, divine, supernatural etcetera kinds of creative forces, whereas *nature naturata* comprehends animate and inanimate and biotic and abiotic and all kinds of flora and fauna.

Carolyn Merchant, in *The Death of Nature* (1980) mentions the history of human understanding of nature. Until the 16th century, humans believed that the earth was a living organism that governed the self, society, and the universe. This adaptable organismic metaphor promoted the recognition of the interdependence of the self and the community. She states, “The image of an organic cosmos with a living female earth at its center gave way to a mechanistic world view in which nature was reconstituted as dead and passive, to be dominated and controlled by humans” (xvi). Similarly, Donald Worster in *The End of the Earth* (1988) explains the connection between human history and environment. He also talks about the ecological disaster, offering insights and reflections. As he enunciates that, “We are facing a global crisis today, not because of how ecosystems function but rather because of how our ethical system function...historians, along with literary scholars, anthropologists and philosophers can’t do the reforming of course, but they can help with understanding” (15). Further, Bill Mckibben’s *The End of the Nature* (1989) elucidates that Nature is at the end because of the excessive interference of the human being, and this excessive interference of human being is called the Anthropocene age. And this book is also called the first book on global warming. In his work he already warns of the impact of global warming issues. Mckibben highlightens that, “We have changed the atmosphere, and thus we are changing the weather. By changing the weather, we make every spot on earth man-made and

artificial. We have deprived nature of its independence, and that is fatal to its meaning. Nature's independence is its meaning; without it there is nothing but us" (50). He used the term 'Mother Nature' instead of nature. The 'end of nature' means, the end of human existence and human civilization. His other book, entitled *Eearth* (2010) expounds the new name of our 'Eearth' instead of Earth, because we have already degraded, despoiled, destroyed and ruined the beautiful planet 'artfully'. That is why he has propounded the new name of Earth, i.e. 'Eearth'.

Robert Watson in *Back to Nature* (2006) explicates the desire to go back to attain the past and pure nature, which is not feasible. He says, "Making nature an antidote for the complexity of our cognitive ecosystems involves a denial of the indispensable complexity of nature. Ecocriticism must make vivid, as Shakespearean drama often does, the beautiful patterns of our interdependences" (Quot. In Garrard, *The Oxford Handbook of Ecocriticism* 6).

Timothy Morton's *Ecology Without Nature* (2007) discusses the idea of 'Nature' as transcendental and uncanny, which further covers all the areas like philosophy, arts, ethics, and many more. As he explicates, "Nature is getting in the way of properly ecological forms of culture, philosophy, politics, and art" (8). Ecology is not only related to 'natural' things or nature but covers everything that surrounds us. He is also in favors of relinquish the idea of nature.

Michael P. Branch in *Reading the Earth* (1996) discusses the "call for cultural change" to ecocritical study and further suggests that if it is not to talk about through literature and nature than a "move towards a more biocentric worldview, an extension of ethics, a broadening of humans conception of global community to include nonhuman life forms and physical environment" (xiii)

Joseph Meeker was the first who used “literary ecology” in *The Comedy of Survival* (1972). He explicates that human beings should take the responsibility to find out or observe the proper role of literature for human well-being and for future prospects so that we can be able to save natural environment to analyze “the insight it offers in to human relationships with other species and with around us” (3-4). Similarly, Aldo Leopold in *A Sand County Almanac* (1949) explicates that the ethical codes have only focused on finding models of synergy between humans and society. There is an absence of ethics that shows mankind how to connect and relate to animals, plants and land. He suggests the idea of conservation in an entirely different way by defining it as a “state of harmony between men and land” (243). Further, Richard Kerridge in *Writing the Environment* (1998) suggests the importance of culture and ecocriticism and asserts, “The ecocritic wants to track environmental ideas and represents wherever they appear, to see more clearly a debate that seems to be taking place, often part-concealed, in a great many cultural spaces”. (5)

The synchronic and diachronic development of Ecocriticism can be seen through four different waves. Lawrence Buell, in *The Future of Environmental Criticism* (2005) explains the first, two waves of ecocriticism:

[O]ne can identify several trend lines marking an evolution from a “first wave” of ecocriticism to a “second” or newer revisionist wave or waves increasingly evident today. This first-second wave distinction should not, however, be taken as implying a tidy, distinct succession. Most currents set in motion by early ecocriticism continue to run strong, and most forms of second-wave revisionism involve building on as well as quarreling with precursors. In this sense, “palimpsest” would be a better metaphor than “wave.” (17)

Buell (1995) delineates the two waves of ecocriticism, but he also accepts that many facts and ideas overlap between these two waves. The first wave starts in the 1980s. It talks about “nature writing, nature poetry and wilderness fiction” (138). It basically focuses on American and British literature. As Wendell Berry enunciates, “Based on the geographical grounds and with its significant focus on nineteenth-century literature, the first wave was marked from the mid-1980s to the late 1990s and was divided into American and British” (233). In America, many ecocritics, like Ralph W. Emerson, Henry David Thoreau, Margret Fuller etc., worked in the American context of nature and wilderness in literature.

In British counterpart, it is well known as Green Studies, where so many English Romantics’ scholars like John Keats, William Wordsworth, Jonathan Bate etcetera. The second wave starts around mid- 1990s, which focuses on more widespread in transcultural literature and includes rural and urban landscapes and multiple genres. Further, Greg Garrard in *Ecocriticism* (2004) explicates that “Second wave is particularly modern in its breaking down some of the long standing distinctions between human and non-human, questioning these very concepts” (1). In the first and second waves, there are not such distinctive parameters through which to create a boundary. As Berry (2011) explains, the contrasts between these two “Proponents of the second wave, necessarily highlight questions of gender, class, race, and colonialism, challenging first-wave ecocritics who seem more interested in presenting ‘wild’ and untamed nature than ‘protecting the environment’”. (Kerridge 234). The third wave arises after 2000. Slovic expands further on Buell’s wave in third and fourth waves through his “Seasick among the Waves of Ecocriticism” (2016). This phase focuses on ecocriticism from the local to the global or national to the international level and also covers many issues like poverty, racism, gender, posthumanism, animality studies, etcetera. As Slovic (2010) delineates about the third wave as:

[G]lobal concepts of place are being explored in fruitful tension with neo-bioregionalist attachments to specific locales, producing such neologisms as “eco-cosmopolitanism, “rooted cosmopolitanism,” “the global soul,” and “translocality”); strong comparatist impulses are raising questions about the possibility of post-national and post-ethnic visions of human experience of the environment. (7)

Similarly, Swarnalatha Rangarajan’s *Ecocriticism* (2018) enunciates that “the third wave of environmental ecocriticism has seen an explosive diversity of themes, approaches and epistemological positions regarding multiple gendered approaches like ecomasculinism, and queer theory, material ecofeminism, animality studies and post humanism” (10). Later, the fourth wave is also defined by Slovic in ISLE in 2012. He focuses on “[T]he fundamental materiality... of environmental things, places, process, forces and experiences” (*Ecocriticism* 101, 11-12). It explicates how the natural world and the human body are both inherently made of material. These four waves all enunciate the growth and development of ecocriticism as a literary and cultural theory. Rangarajan (2018) explains “ecocriticism may be considered as a continuum which accommodates a wide spectrum of perspectives ranging from the political to the sacred” (8). Further, U. Sumathy in *Ecocriticism in Practice* (2009) explicates ecocriticism as a multidisciplinary knowledge domain that interfaces with numerous other discourses. He also enunciates about ecodrama, ecofiction and ecopoetry etcetera. Rayson K. Alex, in “A Survey of the Phases of Indian Ecocriticism” (2014) explicates that Indian ecocriticism is majorly influenced by Western ecocriticism. He “calls for a commitment to a regional approach in Indian ecocriticism and points to social issues that ecocriticism in India needs to address in the near future: land, ethnicity, sustainability, poverty, terrorism, religious plurality, caste, water policies, and education” (1). Similarly, Estok Simon C. in “Introduction to New Work in Ecocriticism”

(2014) explains that the larger concept of ecocriticism was developed by Western environmentalists and afterward extended all around the world. Simon is well aware of the current situation of global warming and so many other issues that we are facing due to the degradation of nature or the environment. Further, Simon warns the society that “we know much, but there is a lot that we do not know, and we live in dangerous times” (1).

Literature widens its scope by showing its concern for ecocriticism. And so many ecocritics, environmentalists, social activists, philosophers and many more have already discussed or are discussing these issues day by day. It is our sole responsibility to save the environment if we want to survive. The repercussions of the environmental degradations have already been seen through floods, heavy rains, cyclones, earthquakes, extreme winters or summers and many more. It represents the environmental awareness. Now it's time to take action to save our 'Mother Earth,' otherwise it will become too late.

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